

Inventory and risk characterization of urban runoff pollutants in Europe

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Chemical fingerprints reveal pollution sources in surface runoff.
- Tire-derived contaminants are widespread in urban runoff across Europe.
- Several pollutants exceed predicted no-effect concentrations in urban runoff.
- Metals are the primary drivers of ecological risk in urban runoff.
- In-silico approach used to identify priority contaminants of emerging concern.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Urban runoff
Ecological risk assessment
Contaminants of emerging concern
High-resolution mass spectrometry
Chemical pollutants

ABSTRACT

Urban runoff is a major pathway for chemical pollutants to enter aquatic ecosystems, yet the occurrences and risks of both conventional pollutants and contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) remain poorly characterized. In this study, we analyzed 34 urban runoff samples from multiple European catchment types using a combination of reversed-phase liquid chromatography (RP-LC) and hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC) coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) for characterization of dissolved organic pollutants, alongside inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) for quantification of trace elements. Street runoff was dominated by heavy metals and tire-derived compounds, including 6PPD-quinone (up to 0.57 µg/L) and 1,3-diphenylguanidine (up to 22.4 µg/L). Benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid was found in 91% of samples up to 153 µg/L, significantly higher than previously reported concentrations in urban runoff. Several wastewater-associated compounds were also common, suggesting contributions from pharmaceutical residues and public urination in surface runoff, and misconnected pipes in separated sewage networks. Risk assessment revealed

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2026.125680>

Received 4 December 2025; Received in revised form 30 January 2026; Accepted 2 March 2026

Available online 3 March 2026

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several compounds exceeding predicted no-effect concentrations (PNEC) with the highest risk associated with the metals Al (up to 1.1×10^4 times PNEC), Cu (8.9×10^3 times PNEC), and Zn (2.7×10^3 times PNEC). Among CECs, clarithromycin (up to 539 times PNEC), 6PPD-quinone (49 times PNEC), and benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid (32 times PNEC) posed the greatest risks. Our findings highlight urban runoff as an environmental concern, with metals, pharmaceuticals, and tire compounds as key drivers of ecological risks.

1. Introduction

Urban runoff pollutants originate from multiple sources in the urban environment such as vehicle traffic (Gasperi et al., 2022; A. Müller et al., 2022), building materials (Wicke et al., 2022), roofs (De Buyck et al., 2021), and wastewater (Mutzner et al., 2022). These sources release conventional pollutants, such as heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) that have a long monitoring history in urban runoff (Müller et al., 2020). There is also a growing list of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) detected in urban runoff, which are micropollutants not included in routine monitoring programs but may pose significant environmental risks.

The large volumes of urban runoff generated during rain events put significant pressure on water management infrastructure, but clear and efficient decision support-systems based on available pollution knowledge, such as GIS-based platforms linking pollution patterns with land use, are lacking to support the implementation of suitable management and treatment technologies.

A striking example of the ecological risks associated with urban runoff is the mass mortality of spawning coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) in the U.S., linked to vehicle-derived pollutants (Peter et al., 2018), particularly the tire-additive degradation product 2-anilino-5-(4-methylpentan-2-ylamino) cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione (6PPD-quinone) (Tian et al., 2021). 6PPD-quinone has since been detected in matrices ranging from groundwater (Zhang et al., 2023) to human urine (Du et al., 2022), which underlines the widespread environmental impact of urban runoff and its potential to contaminate both aquatic ecosystems and groundwater reserves.

Typical wastewater pollutants have also been frequently reported in urban runoff. For example, caffeine was detected in 96 % of stormwater samples in a U.S.-wide survey (Masoner et al., 2019). Likely sources for this group of pollutants include public urination, littering and mis-connected sewage pipes (Bollmann et al., 2019; Müller et al., 2020; Mutzner et al., 2022). This demonstrates the need for broad monitoring of pollutants to detect also unexpected compounds that can occur at specific runoff sites.

Although several studies have documented the occurrence of CECs in urban runoff (Challis et al., 2021; De Buyck et al., 2021; Gasperi et al., 2022; Masoner et al., 2019; Müller et al., 2020; Wicke et al., 2021), important knowledge gaps remain regarding their sources and ecological risks based on environmental concentrations, persistency, and toxicological effects. These gaps stem from the heterogeneous nature of runoff, which varies significantly between catchment areas and rain events (Mutzner et al., 2022), and from methodological limitations, including challenges of analyzing very mobile CECs and a lack of toxicological data for risk evaluation.

Most analytical studies of organic runoff pollutants rely on gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) for non-polar pollutants found on the particulate fraction (Zgheib et al., 2011) or reversed phase liquid chromatography-MS (RP-LC-MS) for dissolved semi-polar to polar compounds (Challis et al., 2021; Wicke et al., 2022). These methods have also been combined, as in the recent paper by Santana-Viera et al. (2025) that leverages their complementarity for runoff analysis. However, very polar compounds, such as melamine and short-chained per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), are not retained on RP columns and therefore not covered by most monitoring programs (Reemtsma et al., 2016). Instead, alternative separation techniques such as supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC) or hydrophilic interaction liquid

chromatography (HILIC) can retain these highly mobile compounds. While SFC and HILIC have been used in wastewater and surface water studies (Zahn et al., 2019; Tisler et al., 2025), they remain largely unexplored for urban runoff, leaving very mobile pollutants poorly characterized (Mutzner et al., 2023). Combining RP-LC—HRMS and HILIC—HRMS therefore gives broader coverage of dissolved organic pollutants, capturing both semi-polar and very polar compounds that are otherwise overlooked (Mottaghiasheh et al., 2025).

Even with methods for accurate quantification, the essential step of estimating environmental toxicity remains a challenge due to lack of toxicological knowledge. This is especially relevant for CECs, which have not yet been thoroughly characterized. To overcome this gap, predicted toxicity values can be used to prioritize CECs for further analysis and experimental toxicological tests. Several modelling approaches exist which estimate toxicity on an organism level (Peets et al., 2022) or for specific endpoints derived from toxicity assays (Arturi et al., 2025) based on high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) spectra. These tools help bridge the data gap and support risk assessments, particularly for CECs that are not yet part of regulatory monitoring.

In this study, we present a multi-catchment investigation of urban runoff from six European cities across different seasons to evaluate pollution sources and associated risks of runoff pollutants. By combining broad-spectrum chemical analysis using multiple analytical platforms with risk assessment based on a combination of experimental and predicted toxicity values, we provide novel insights into runoff pollutants beyond those obtainable using a single method or focusing on a single catchment type. Data was stored on a GIS-based web system developed to support urban runoff management. Our results demonstrate that untreated urban runoff frequently contains both conventional pollutants and CECs, with metals and tire-derived compounds driving the ecological risks.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Urban runoff sampling

The sampling procedure has previously been described in Molnár Karlsson and Christensen (2025). Briefly, thirty-four runoff samples were collected in Santander (Sa; Spain), Pontedera (Po; Italy), Ljubljana (Lj; Slovenia), Riga (Ri; Latvia), Odense (Od; Denmark), and Copenhagen (Co; Denmark) (Fig. 1). Sampling stations were selected to cover a wide range of catchment types, including both large- and small-scale sources from individual buildings and streets to combined sewer overflow (CSO) discharge points collecting city-wide wastewater and runoff (sample details and full dataset included in SI2). Samples were grouped according to the main catchment type as either street runoff (collected from roads and paved surfaces), roof runoff (from drainpipes or separated sewage systems), residential areas (from suburban areas with a mixture of roads, buildings, and green urban areas), or CSO (from sewage pipes containing a mix of surface runoff and wastewater).

Runoff samples were collected during the first 120 min of rainfall events, with 250 mL sub-samples collected at 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 120 min. Precipitation was measured on-site using a tipping bucket rain gauge for most events; where unavailable, local meteorological data were used for estimation. After collection, samples were stored and transported dark at <5 °C for up to 72 h prior to processing. Two samples (Po01 and Po05) were stored for 7 days before processing due to shipping delay.

Field blanks were collected approximately every 10 runoff samples and consisted of LC-MS grade water amended with 300 mg/L CaCl₂ to mimic the ionic strength of runoff. The field blanks were poured into similar glassware as used for regular runoff samples and underwent the same sample preparation and analysis steps described in Section 2.3.

2.2. Sample handling and standard analysis

In the laboratory, 250 mL sub-sample bottles were shaken to suspend particles, and 50 mL aliquots were transferred by pouring for pH, conductivity, and turbidity measurements. The remaining sub-samples were combined in a 4 L beaker to create a composite sample. The volume required for chemical analysis (1 L for RP-LC–HRMS, 30 mL for inductively coupled plasma (ICP)-MS, 100 mL for HILIC–HRMS) were transferred with a 20 mL glass pipette. To ensure homogeneous distribution of particles, aliquots were transferred from the beaker while stirring with a magnetic stir bar.

Acid-soluble trace elements were quantified by acidifying 30-mL unfiltered aliquots with nitric acid according to DS 250:2003, followed by ICP-MS analysis according to DS/EN ISO 17294m:2016 (Eurofins Environment, Denmark).

Turbidity, pH, and conductivity were determined for all composite samples as well as all individual sub-samples. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and total organic carbon (TOC) were determined for all composite samples. For detailed method descriptions, see SI1.

Samples for HILIC-analysis were stored in the freezer (−18 °C) until further sample treatment, whereas samples for RP-LC analysis were

processed immediately.

2.3. Target and suspect screening analysis by RP-LC–HRMS

A standard mixture of 102 runoff-relevant compounds, including pesticides, PFAS, industrial chemicals, and tire additives (listed in SI3), was used for targeted analysis. Quantification was performed using the internal standard (IS) method with a mix of 23 isotopically labelled compounds. All standards were prepared in methanol (Honeywell Riedel-de Haen) and stored at −18 °C.

Runoff sample preparation involved solid-phase extraction (SPE) using a protocol previously described in Molnár Karlsson and Christensen (2025). Briefly, 1 L of each sample was sequentially filtered through 1.6 μm and 0.7 μm glass fiber filters (Whatman), and the filtrate was subjected to multi-layer SPE for clean-up and enrichment.

Based on earlier findings linking matrix effects to antecedent dry periods (Molnár Karlsson and Christensen, 2025), extracts were enriched either 50 × or 10 × with lower enrichment used for samples containing a large proportion of wastewater or collected after >10 dry days. Two samples (Po05, Ri02) were initially analyzed at 50 × enrichment but re-analyzed at 2.5 × enrichment, since 1,3-diphenylguanidine was initially outside the linear range. IS-mix was spiked post-extraction to reach a final concentration of 2–100 μg/L, depending on ionization efficiency. The reason for spiking post-extraction was to allow toxicological experiments of SPE extracts (not included in this study). A pooled quality control (QC_{pooled}) sample was prepared by combining all extracts.

Fig. 1. Urban runoff samples collected from four characteristic source types in six European cities. Sampling sites are categorized into street, roof, residential, and combined sewer overflows (CSO), as indicated by color-coded circles. The number of samples collected from each source type is indicated inside the circles next to the corresponding sampling locations: Odense and Copenhagen (DK), Riga (LV), Ljubljana (SI), Pontedera (IT), and Santander (ES).

Analysis was performed on a Vanquish Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatograph (UHPLC) with an Orbitrap Exploris 240 (Thermo Scientific). Chromatographic separation was done using a BEH C18 column (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m particle size) (Waters) with a 25-min binary gradient: Solvent A (0.1 % formic acid (Fisher Chemicals) in LC-MS grade water (Honeywell Riedel-de Haen)) and solvent B (0.1 % formic acid in acetonitrile (Chemsolute)) at 0.3 mL/min (details in SI1). Data-independent acquisition (DIA) was used, alternating between full scan (120,000 resolving power), and all-ion fragmentation (AIF) scans (30,000 resolving power) with stepped collision energies of 20, 40, and 60 eV.

Each sample was analyzed in triplicate spread over the analytical sequence, with QC_{pooled} injections for every eight injections. Calibration standards were analyzed in the beginning of each sequence, and single-point calibration was run during the sequence to monitor instrument drift. Peak integration and quantification of target compounds was performed in TraceFinder (Thermo Scientific). For compounds detected with both target analysis and HILIC—HRMS suspect screening, target analysis results were kept except for melamine and metformin since these compounds were unretained on the RP column.

Deconvolution, alignment, and identification for suspect screening was done using MS Dial (v4.92) (Tsugawa et al., 2015). Main parameters were: 2.5 mDa MS1 tolerance and 5 mDa MS2 tolerance, and 0.2 min alignment retention time tolerance. Features were annotated by matching with a suspect list containing >1500 runoff-relevant compounds (included in SI3) based on reference MSMS spectra from the MassBank of North America (MoNA) or, where unavailable, in-silico fragmentation. Suspect compounds were selected based on occurrence in previous studies on environmental water pollutants (Du et al., 2020; Gasperi et al., 2022; Masoner et al., 2019; Peter et al., 2022; Saifur and Gardner, 2021; Wang et al., 2020; Wicke et al., 2021; Zgheib et al., 2011). Identifications were inspected manually and identification confidence scores (0–100) were assigned according to a workflow adapted from Tisler et al. (2022): Accurate precursor mass (20 points for <3 ppm difference, 10 for <5 ppm), matching library spectra (15–30 points), retention time (10 points), plausibility based on occurrence and use (10 points), confirmation with standard (30 points). Peak areas for identified suspects were used to characterize source pollution, but not for calculating risk quotients.

2.4. Suspect screening using HILIC

For HILIC—HRMS analysis, frozen samples were thawed at 5 °C, and 100 μ L internal standard mix (IS-mix1) containing 13 isotope-labelled standards 0.2 mg/L in methanol (SI3) were added to 100 mL sample. Samples were pre-concentrated by vacuum-assisted evaporative concentration (VEC) using a Syncore® Analyst R-12 (BÜCHI Labortechnik AG) using the method by Mechelke et al. (2019) except that glass containers without residual volume were used and samples were evaporated to complete dryness and redissolved in acetonitrile containing 5 mM NH₄formate and 5 % water. To redissolve, 1 mL was added and the container was vortex-stirred before transferring the solvent to a 4 mL-vial. This was repeated two additional times. The combined samples were centrifuged (10 min, 5000 rpm), and 1000 μ L was transferred to a UPLC-vial and spiked with 50 μ L IS-mix2 (BAC12-D₅, ¹³C₃—melamine, 0.2 μ g/L).

Samples were analyzed on Elute OLE UHPLC coupled to a TimsTOF equipped with ESI ion source (Bruker Daltonics). The HILIC separation was performed on an ACQUITY Premier UPLC BEH Amide column (Waters, 130 Å, 1.7 μ m, 2.1 mm x 100 mm) using a 25-min binary gradient of acetonitrile/water both buffered with 5 mM NH₄ formate (details in SI1).

The timsTOF was operated in qTOF only mode at acquisition from *m/z* 30–1000. MSMS-data were acquired in auto MSMS mode with collision energy altering between 24 and 36 eV of the four highest intensity ions. Precursor ions were excluded after three fragmentations with a 0.2 min

dynamic exclusion window. With every sample batch minimum 3 laboratory blanks were included in the sample processing and analysis. All samples were injected in triplicate, and a pooled sample was analyzed for every 8th injection to monitor system performance.

Feature detection and annotation was performed in Metaboscope 2023b (Bruker Daltonics) using the T-ReX 3D® feature finding algorithm with an intensity threshold of 5000 counts and minimum peak width of six datapoints. Detected features were considered if present in all three replicate injections with an average intensity at least three times higher than the maximum in blank samples. Annotation was performed using a suspect list of >1200 runoff-relevant compounds with MSMS reference spectra from in-house database or Massbank EU (June 2024) and, if no experimental spectra was available, in-silico fragmentation using MetFrag (Ruttkies et al., 2016).

HILIC results have been reported as peak intensity divided by the peak intensity of the internal standard atrazine-desethyl-d₅, which was added to each sample prior to evaporation. The suspect screening results were used to characterize source pollution, but not for calculating risk quotients. Level of confidence is displayed according to the levels defined by Schymanski et al. (2014).

2.5. Calculating environmental risk quotients

LC₅₀ values for target compounds were obtained from the ECOTOX knowledgebase (Olker et al., 2022) for three aquatic organisms: fish, *Daphnia magna*, and green algae (*Raphidocelis subcapitata*). For fish, data from both *Oncorhynchus* spp. and *Pimephales promelas* were used to increase the number of experimental values and provide a more generalized toxicity estimate. When multiple LC₅₀ values were available for a compound, the arithmetic mean was used.

For compounds lacking experimental fish toxicity data, LC₅₀ values were predicted using MS2Tox (Peets et al., 2022). Predicted and experimentally derived LC₅₀ values were compared (Fig. SI1), which showed good overall correlation ($R^2 = 0.44$), except for 6PPD-quinone, which showed markedly higher toxicity to fish, consistent with its known acute toxicity for some fish species (Tian et al., 2021).

Risk quotients (RQs) were calculated using the following equation:

$$RQ = \frac{MEC}{PNEC} \quad (1)$$

Where MEC is the measured environmental concentration, and PNEC (predicted no effect concentration) is calculated as LC₅₀ divided by an assessment factor of 1000. All LC₅₀ values and calculated RQs are listed in SI3. For metal(loids), the measured concentrations likely over-estimated the bioavailable concentration compared to other methods, since samples were acidified without prior filtration.

2.6. Data management and -analysis

The GIS-based framework was developed within an AI-assisted digital urban runoff management platform (outlined in Figs. SI2–3). A hierarchical data model, based on the information presented in SI2, was designed to harmonize inputs and link laboratory results with sample meta-data. The model was used for storing data into the digital platform structured around five core concepts: 1) Site, 2) Station, 3) Sampling point, 4) Sample, and 5) Analysis (additional information available by contacting authors).

Correlation analysis and identification of clusters was done using the Python script in SI1. Spearman correlations were calculated between all variables in the dataset (compounds and sample meta-data) and hierarchical clustering was performed on the correlation scores to determine the top 3 largest clusters based on a maximum distance of 2 in the dendrogram. For the calculations, only compounds with ≥ 3 detections were included to avoid false correlations caused by too few data points (e.g. between compounds detected only in a single sample). Similarly,

only suspects with ID score >50 (RP-LC) or \geq level 2 (HILIC) were included to remove compounds with highly uncertain annotation. After these filtering steps, one overlapping compound (*N,N-dimethyldecylamine oxide) remained in both the RP-LC–HRMS and HILIC–HRMS suspect screenings; both occurrences were kept for later calculations. In the discussion, we mark suspect screening compound names with * to differentiate from compounds quantified with target analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Pollutant groups in urban runoff

The results showed large variations both within and between runoff types (Fig. 2; see also grouped heatmap in Fig. SI4). This variation captures a realistic picture of urban runoff pollution: Since sampling was done across different seasons and rain events, the results show average pollution levels rather than just extremes, including the effects of peak rain events as well as lengthy autumn and winter rains.

CSO and street runoff samples generally contained higher pollutant concentrations (for target compounds) and signals (for suspects) than roof and residential samples, though there were exceptions for individual compounds. For example, tributyl phosphate was found predominantly in roof samples where it was detected in two out of four samples in concentrations from 0.13–0.14 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Tributyl phosphate could originate from building materials where it is used as a flame retardant and plasticizer in a wide range of materials, or from background levels in rain as tributyl phosphate has previously been reported in concentrations up to 0.14 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in rain samples (Polyakova et al., 2018).

Both pharmaceuticals and the quaternary ammonium compounds (QACs) and detergents were predominantly found in CSO samples, which is expected as both groups are abundant in household wastewater (Kilpinen et al., 2023). Paracetamol, a typical wastewater indicator, was detected in all CSO samples in concentrations up to 196 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Co12), which is similar to previously reported concentrations from 121–242 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in influent wastewater (Kilpinen et al., 2023). This suggests that wastewater was the major contribution in the sample, despite being collected during a rain event. On the other hand, Lj03 and Od07 showed lower abundance of paracetamol (0.05 and 6.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$, respectively),

suggesting low proportion of domestic wastewater, possibly because of dilution with surface runoff.

While tire and anticorrosion compounds were predominantly found in street runoff samples, originating from vehicle and traffic emissions (Challis et al., 2021; Gasperi et al., 2022; Peter et al., 2018), several industry compounds were also frequent in CSO where they could originate from the surface runoff fraction or other sources. For example, benzotriazoles (1H-benzotriazole, 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole and *4-methylbenzotriazole, ID score 60) have a wide range of applications, including as UV stabilizers and corrosion inhibitors both for cars and in dishwashing tabs (Vetter and Lorenz, 2013). This can explain the high occurrence in CSO and street runoff samples, as 1H-benzotriazole was found in all CSO samples up to 1.47 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and in 78 % of street runoff up to 2.7 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Other compound groups (pesticides, industrial compounds, and trace elements) showed more variation between runoff types, reflecting site-specific uses and characteristics. For example, the roof runoff sample Co10 had highest concentration of Pb (51 $\mu\text{g/L}$), which was not detected in other roof samples, likely originating from metal sheets or lead-containing glazing of roof tiles at Co10. Other trace elements were indicative of vehicle traffic, as shown in Fig. 3 and discussed in the following sections.

Overall, trace element concentrations were comparable with similar studies analyzing both the dissolved and particulate fraction. For Al, which was the most abundant element in this study with concentrations up to 23 mg/L, our results were comparable with a previous study measuring from 6–253 mg/L in urban snowmelt (A. Müller et al., 2022). However, our results were generally higher than studies analyzing only the dissolved fraction (A. Müller et al., 2022; Zgheib et al., 2011). In their comparison of trace elements in the dissolved and particulate fraction of urban watershed samples, Zgheib et al. (2011) found 38 $\mu\text{g/L}$ average Zn concentration in the dissolved fraction but 305 $\mu\text{g/L}$ when combining the dissolved and particulate fraction. This is similar to the average 232 $\mu\text{g/L}$ measured in our study, reflecting the extraction of both dissolved and weakly bound species by acidification of samples with particles. Similar trends were found for Cr, Cu and Pb, which Zgheib et al. (2011) did not detect above limit of quantification (LOQ) in any of the dissolved fractions but found in the combined fractions with average concentrations of: Cr 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (average 9.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in our study),

Fig. 2. Boxplot showing range-scaled (0–1) distribution of chemical compound classes for different groups of runoff samples from combined sewer overflows (CSO, $n = 6$), residential areas ($n = 6$), roof ($n = 4$), and street runoff ($n = 18$). Whiskers indicate 5 % and 95 % percentiles. Only variables with ≥ 2 detections were included.

Fig. 3. Spearman correlation heatmap with dendrogram of chemical and environmental variables measured in 34 urban runoff samples (same variables on x- and y-axis). Hierarchical clustering was applied to group variables based on their correlation profiles. The heatmap shows pairwise Spearman correlation coefficients, with red indicating positive correlations and blue negative correlations. Top three clusters are shown, based on number of variables with max distance = 2. Cluster 1 (highlighted in orange) includes runoff-associated pollutants such as 1,3-diphenylguanidine, 6PPD-quinone, benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid, Ni, and Zn. Cluster 2 (green) includes compounds such as nicotine, caffeine, and DEET. Cluster 3 (blue) includes typical wastewater compounds, such as acesulfame and pharmaceuticals. Only variables with ≥ 3 detections and ID score for suspects >50 (RP-LC) or \geq level 2 (HILIC) were included.

Cu 118 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (average 43 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in our study), and Pb 66 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (average 11 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in our study). While we did not analyze the dissolved fraction separately, the correspondence with earlier findings suggest that the measured concentrations in our study were also higher than what would be derived from analyzing the dissolved fraction alone.

For pesticides, some compounds were characteristic of CSO, including terbutryn which was detected in all CSO samples with concentration up to 0.17 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Po01). This corresponds well with previously reported detection frequencies ($>90\%$) and concentrations (up to 0.16 $\mu\text{g/L}$) in wastewater (Kilpinen et al., 2023). Terbutryn has a wide range of biocide applications, including as an herbicide and in façade paintings and plaster, and its occurrence in wastewater has previously been linked to household activities, such as washing of paint brushes (Bollmann et al., 2014; Singer et al., 2010). Other pesticides, such as N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide (DEET) and *2,4-dinitrophenol (60 ID points), were found across all runoff types. Since there are no registered pesticides containing 2,4-dinitrophenol in the EU, pesticide application is an unlikely explanation for the widespread occurrence of this compound. Exhaust from combustion engines is a more likely source, since combustion can generate various nitrophenols including 2,4-dinitrophenol.

DEET was detected in 91 % of all samples, though below the quantification limit (31 ng/L) in many samples. This corresponds to previous studies detecting DEET in 98 % of stormwater samples in the U.S. (Masoner et al., 2019). DEET is predominantly known as a skin insect repellent, which does not explain its widespread occurrence, particularly in surface runoff during the winter months. A likely source is from plastic materials, as DEET has been shown to leach from plastic bottles where it could originate from impurities or transformation of plasticizers (Tisler and Christensen, 2022).

3.2. Characteristic pollution sources

Correlation analysis revealed characteristic clusters of compounds

and parameters with similar occurrences in runoff samples (Fig. 3). Cluster 1 (marked orange) included tire-derived pollutants such as benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid and 6PPD-quinone, and heavy metals (Cr, Cu, Ni, Cd, Al, V, Co, Pb, Sb). While heavy metals have several urban sources, including metal surfaces, our results correspond to previous studies linking heavy metals to vehicle traffic (Challis et al., 2021; Gasperi et al., 2022; K. Müller et al., 2022; Peter et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2020). Tire-related sources include abrasion of tire materials (Cd, Cu, Zn) and brakes (Cd, Pb, Cu, Ni, Sb, Zn) (Gasperi et al., 2022; Müller et al., 2020). For example, Sb, which is used in brake pads, was measured up to 18 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in street runoff (Po05), comparable to previously reported concentrations of Sb from 1.3 to 39.8 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in street runoff (Gasperi et al., 2022). Of the CECs, Benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid, a tire transformation product, was one of the most abundant organic compounds with detection in 91 % of samples at concentrations up to 153 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Po05) which is comparable to the median 52.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ reported in street runoff (Fuchte et al., 2022), but significantly higher than the 0.82 $\mu\text{g/L}$ reported in urban runoff by Tian et al. (2020).

Compounds in cluster 1 were found predominantly in street runoff samples (Fig. 4), which is consistent with their emission from vehicle traffic. However, they were also found in other types, particularly CSO which is logical since road runoff forms a major part of the input during rain events, and e.g. 1,3-diphenylguanidine is ubiquitous in surface waters (Zahn et al., 2019).

Cluster 3 (marked blue in Fig. 3) was predominantly found in CSO samples and included typical wastewater compounds, such as pharmaceuticals and the artificial sweetener acesulfame. Acesulfame was also found in relatively high concentration in a storm drain (Co01; 0.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$), compared with max 1.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in CSO), which suggests an input of wastewater in Co01. Since Co01 was collected from a storm drain in the inner-city area, possible sources of typical wastewater compound include public urination or misconnected pipes (Müller et al., 2020; Mutzner et al., 2022).

Fig. 4. Boxplot showing range scaled concentrations (targets) or signal intensities (suspects) of compounds associated with the three top clusters identified by hierarchical clustering of Spearman correlations. Each box represents the distribution of compounds within an individual sample, with circles showing outlying observations (outside $1.5 \times$ interquartile range). Colors indicate sample source.

Contrary to the other clusters, there was no obvious link to sample or compound groups for cluster 2 (marked green in Fig. 3). Since this cluster included compounds such as benzotriazoles which, as previously discussed, can come from multiple sources, it is likely that it is not indicative of a specific type of runoff. Other compounds included nicotine and caffeine, which are ubiquitous in urban environments and could correlate with hidden background factors. For example, population density and the presence of nearby bus stops has been shown to affect nicotine concentrations in surface runoff (Venohr et al., 2025). Overall, this suggests that cluster 2 contains a varied group of compounds from different sources, including wastewater and surface runoff.

3.3. Risk assessment of urban runoff pollutants and sources

Twenty-five target pollutants exceeded RQ values of 1, corresponding to a measured concentration above PNECs (Fig. 5). While these RQs are based on limited experimental toxicity data, and thus represent estimated rather than absolute risks, they provide a valuable indication of potentially harmful pollutants and pollution sources based on individual compounds. Similarly, the toxicity of mixtures was not included and remains difficult to predict as previous work has demonstrated additive effects, but also competition, inhibition and potentiation effects of the presence of several contaminants in the same matrix (Mezzelani et al., 2025).

Metals showed the highest overall RQ with values up to 1.1×10^4 for fish (Al in Po05), 8.9×10^3 for Daphnia (Cu, Po05) and 2.7×10^3 for green algae (Zn, Co02). These results are consistent with previous reports showing high RQs for several metals (including Cu, Zn, Ni, and Pb)

in stormwater (Mutzner et al., 2022). Similarly, Johnson et al. (2017) found Cu, Al, and Zn to be the three highest ranked chemicals of concern in UK rivers. As previously discussed, determined metal concentrations were higher than derived from analyzing only the dissolved fraction due to the extraction of samples with particles. This demonstrates the effect of the analytical method on estimations of RQ, which is important when comparing between studies or with regulatory guidelines. It is also relevant to note when comparing the estimated RQ of metals and organic micropollutants, since the organic compounds quantified with RP-LC–HRMS were extracted after filtration and therefore include only the dissolved phase.

Of the dissolved organic pollutants, 6PPD-quinone showed the highest RQ for fish (up to 49, corresponding to $0.57 \mu\text{g/L}$). The measurements are similar to previously reported concentrations of up to $0.6 \mu\text{g/L}$ in road runoff (Tian et al., 2021) and $0.086\text{--}1.4 \mu\text{g/L}$ in urban snowmelt (Challis et al., 2021). An LC_{50} value of $11.5 \mu\text{g/L}$ was used in our calculations, reflecting an average of several species. However, LC_{50} values can vary widely, with some species (chinook salmon) showing low sensitivity towards 6PPD-quinone ($>67 \mu\text{g/L}$) (Lo et al., 2023) while others such as coho salmon, exhibit much higher sensitivity ($\text{LC}_{50} = 0.096 \mu\text{g/L}$) (Tian et al., 2021). Applying a worst-case LC_{50} values would yield substantially higher RQs. Similarly, the derived RQ was likely lower than what would be obtained if the particle fraction was included, since leaching from tire particles constitutes a major source of 6PPD-quinone and other rubber compounds (K. Müller et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2021).

The antibiotic clarithromycin also showed high environmental risk with a concentration of $1.08 \mu\text{g/L}$ (Po01) resulting in an RQ of 539 for

Fig. 5. Estimated risk quotients (RQs) for fish (*Oncorhynchus* spp. and *Pimephales promelas*), *Daphnia magna*, and green algae (*Raphidocelis subcapitata*) for compounds with maximum RQ > 0.1. Values are plotted on a logarithmic scale. RQs were calculated using experimental LC₅₀ data when available; for fish, predicted toxicity values were applied when experimental data were lacking. Percent occurrence for each compound in all samples is shown in parenthesis next to compound name.

green algae. Previous studies have reported similar findings, with clarithromycin one-order-of-magnitude above PNEC in surface water (Isidori et al., 2005). Besides acute toxic effects, clarithromycin may promote antibiotic-resistance bacteria, a risk not included in this study. Terbutryn also showed high algal toxicity, with RQs up to 64, over 800 times higher than its RQ for fish, showcasing the importance of organism-specific sensitivity in risk evaluations.

Accumulated RQs in individual samples ranged from 12 (Sa01) to 2.5×10^4 (Po05), which demonstrates the high variability in runoff samples. For metals (Fig. 6, left), the highest RQs were observed in CSO and street runoff samples. However, all four roof samples also had high total RQ ($2.2 \times 10^2 - 2.3 \times 10^3$), primarily due to Zn which could originate

from roof materials. These results demonstrate the potential environmental risks associated with urban runoff discharges, even from seemingly benign sources such as roofs.

For organic micropollutants (Fig. 6, right), different compounds were driving RQs between sample groups, reflecting the source-specific compound clusters related to CSO and street runoff samples. In CSO samples, clarithromycin was the dominant contributor to overall risk, which is consistent with previous studies demonstrating its occurrence in wastewater effluents (Kilpinen et al., 2023). Despite its low concentration in the samples, clarithromycin contributed significantly to the RQ due to its high algae toxicity (LC₅₀ = 2 µg/L) reported by Isidori et al. (2005). Notably, a RQ of 12.5 was also found for clarithromycin in street

Fig. 6. Stacked bar plots showing the maximum RQs across samples for the five dominant metals (left) and organic micropollutants (right) in urban runoff samples from streets, CSOs, roof, and residential areas. The selected pollutants account for 98 % of the total RQ for the target metals and 95 % for the target organics, based on the most sensitive species in each case. Note that the x-axis scales differ between panel A and B.

runoff sample Po03, though the measurement (25 ng/L) was below LOQ (44 ng/L). Since Po03 was collected from the street surface near a hospital entrance, transfer of medicinal residues from the shoe soles, medicinal packaging, or spitting may have introduced pharmaceuticals into the surface runoff sample.

In contrast, high RQs in street runoff were primary due to tire-related contaminants, 6PPD-quinone, benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid, and 1,3-diphenylguanidine, underlining the environmental risks with street traffic emissions (Peter et al., 2018; Saifur and Gardner, 2021; Tian et al., 2020). While 6PPD-quinone and 1,3-diphenylguanidine have recently attracted regulatory and scientific attention, benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid remains less studied. Since no experimental toxicity values were available in the ECOTOX knowledgebase, our risk assessment relied on a predicted value. With predicted LC_{50} for fish around 4.8 mg/L, our results suggest that benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid has very high environmental relevance with $RQ > 1$ in 38 % of all samples, and in 67 % of street runoff samples specifically. This highlights the need for further studies into this compound and determination of experimental toxicity values.

4. Conclusion

This study determined the chemical composition and ecological risks of urban runoff from multiple European catchments using a combination of experimental and predicted toxicity data. Clustering of pollutants identified source-specific profiles, with combined sewer overflows characterized by wastewater-associated compounds and street runoff by traffic-related emissions. The presence of wastewater indicators in several surface runoff samples indicated inputs from public urination, pharmaceutical residues, and misconnected sewage pipes, which might be a widespread source in urban runoff.

Metals, in particular Al, Cu, and Zn, were the main contributors to ecological risk, with cumulative RQ up to 2.4×10^4 in street runoff.

Among organic contaminants, tire-related compounds such as 6PPD-quinone, 1,3-diphenylguanidine, and benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid, accounted for a substantial proportion of estimated risks and were frequently detected. The widespread detection and predicted risk of benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid indicate that it is an environmentally relevant compound requiring further investigation.

These results show that untreated urban runoff poses ecological risks and that management of discharges from combined sewer overflows and streets is essential to protect recipient ecosystems. Future work should provide experimental toxicity data for poorly characterized emerging contaminants and evaluate the effects of pollutant mixtures. The particulate fraction, including leaching and toxicological effects of tire rubber particles, requires particular attention in subsequent studies.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT for proofreading and developing Python scripts for data analysis and visualization. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thomas Molnár Karlsson: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ulla E. Bollmann:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Tina Kosjek:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Agnese Arāja:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Maris Bertiņš:** Resources. **Stefano Tempestini:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Jesús F. Águila:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Nicolás Morales:** Writing –

review & editing, Resources. **Rubén Díez-Montero:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Anders R. Johnsen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jan H. Christensen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Thomas Karlsson reports financial support was provided by European Union and the Novo Nordisk Foundation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This study is a contribution to the European Union's Horizon Europe project D4RUNOFF project under grant agreement no 101060638. Research infrastructure was supported by the Novo Nordisk Foundation (grant NNF22OC0075387) for the project "Chemical and Toxicological Fingerprinting Infrastructure (Contaminomics)".

The authors would also like to thank the staff at Aqualia (Spain), Acque Spa (Italy), Vandcenter Syd (Denmark) for contributing with sampling during the rain events.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.watres.2026.125680](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2026.125680).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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